

TEACHING THE ENGLISH LANGUAGE WITH MODERN TECHNOLOGIES AND WEBSITES

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ANNOTATION

This article is about the role of modern technology and websites in English language teaching, as well as successful approaches to foreign language teaching.

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INTRODUCTION

Today, our country, like many advanced countries, raises to the level of state policy the teaching of several foreign languages in addition to the state language to all strata of its population, and the wide range of foreign language learning and teaching is developing a number of draft laws to ensure its active participation in major reforms. Consequently, as a logical continuation of these ideas, the Presidential Decree "On measures to further improve the system of teaching foreign languages" adopted on December 10, 2012 expanded the opportunities for learning foreign languages [1]. Nowadays, most public and private companies require candidates with good English and relevant qualifications. For this reason, the role of the English language in school curricula is crucial, and the government is paying great attention to the teaching of the English language in schools and universities of Uzbekistan. English is taught as a compulsory subject in universities and schools of Uzbekistan, and the government is making great efforts to promote quality teaching and learning of English [2].

Enhancing the interest of young students in learning English, expanding their existing opportunities, and supporting them will help them learn this language faster. It is necessary to increase

- providing various electronic resources;
- creation of methodological support for language learning in educational institutions;
- increase the efficiency of using existing textbooks;
- attracting strong and qualified specialists to the teaching process;
- adequate introduction of new educational technologies into the educational process;

- focus on student motivation in teaching and control the quality of the evaluation system.

Controlling the quality and efficiency of English language lessons is manifested in the increase in speech expressions in which the main part of the received information is taken from everyday life. Evaluation of the use of innovative technologies in the lesson as a means of language teaching and learning helps to create many positive results and advantages.

Innovation. Innovation (English "innovatsion") is innovation, innovation. Innovative technologies are innovations and changes in the pedagogical process and activities of teachers and students, and have an important aspect in its implementation. The use of innovative technologies is reflected in the work carried out to increase students' thinking, imagination, worldview, interests. According to McCarthy, "the methodology of teaching foreign languages has developed a lot over the past half century. It has been conducted at various times in grammatical translation, audio-linguistic structure, global audiovisual, inductive/deductive, functional, ideational, situational, communicative, immersion, learning/receiving, recommendation, etc. Consequently, as a result of the use of audiovisual tools during the lesson, the ability to remember the semantic meaning of words and use lexical units improves. [3]

Information communication technologies. The role of modern pedagogical technologies and information and communication tools in improving the quality and efficiency of education, in the purposeful organization of game-based lessons that interest students is very large. is becoming an integral part of the process. In order to teach English to young people through a computer, first of all, the teacher himself must be able to use computer technologies at a professional level. including the ability to organize new training programs. In order to become a pedagogue of this level, every foreign language teacher needs to work more on himself in the field of modern technologies. Computer-based English language teaching has several advantages compared to traditional teaching methods. First of all, a computer-based English language learner has four areas of language skills (speaking, listening, writing, and reading). will have the opportunity to test their skills. Currently, this is possible with the help of advanced programs. It is only necessary to be able to properly direct the student to this method of education.

In addition, it has been proven that every rule, every word, every concept unit taught in the teaching of foreign languages with the help of a computer is better stored in the student's memory. the ability to deliver in the form of video makes teaching foreign languages through the computer one of the most effective methods. Therefore,

every teacher needs to use the rich possibilities of the computer in teaching English to his students through the computer. Basically, it is appropriate to use Word and Power Point programs to explain current topics. Because I think that students will understand much easier if the topic is explained using table views through the Word program. In Power Point, students can be more attracted to the topic by showing these topics in audio, picture and video formats.

Educational technologies. One of the main tasks is to improve the teacher's pedagogical skills by mastering modern teaching and learning technologies. With the use of any new technologies, new pedagogical ideas of the teacher begin: the clarity of the systematic, methodological language, the emergence of clear tactics in the teaching methodology. The most important task of the educational process is the student's personal interest. It is necessary to know which technologies should be used in the educational process to obtain the planned results. It is clear that the use of any specific educational technology, no matter how perfect, does not create the most effective conditions for determining and developing students' skills. Pedagogical (educational) technology is a well-thought-out model of educational and pedagogical activity combined with a comfortable environment for students and teachers to design, organize and conduct the educational process. Pedagogical technology includes the implementation of the idea of full control of the educational process [4]. Modern educational technologies include:

- development;
- studying problems;
- multi-level education;
- collective education system;
- technological study of inventive problems;
- research methods in teaching;
- project teaching methods;

Technology used in teaching game styles:

- role-playing, business and other types of educational games;
- cooperative education (community, group work);
- information and communication technologies;

When it comes to design and interactive teaching methods, their combination and integration is considered one of the most effective and efficient tools in the process of teaching English. One of them is the project method. The project method is designed to develop a child's active independent thinking and teach him not only to memorize and reproduce knowledge, but also to apply it in practice. It is important that children learn

to cooperate when working on a project, and cooperative education helps to strengthen mutual support, desire and ability, and students' creative abilities and activities are formed. The project method is a set of educational and knowledge techniques that allow solving certain problems as a result of the mandatory presentation of these results as a result of independent actions of students. The project method is an activity that allows students to express themselves independently, individually or in a group, to test their abilities, the teacher to apply his knowledge in practice, to show the results achieved by the public. This method involves solving interesting problems created by students themselves. For example, "Why am I late for class today?" i.e. "Why am I late for class today?" the question is asked. In this way, students try to express their knowledge through a foreign language, and they do not repeat this situation by showing their trivial reasons to other students [5].

The design method as a pedagogical technology is a technology that includes a combination of research, research, and problem-solving methods. For students, the project is an opportunity to increase their creative potential to the maximum level, and in principle, in order to solve the problem, students should have clear creative, intellectual and communicative skills. Therefore, for the correct use of the project method, extensive training is required, which is carried out in an integrated educational system.

Interactive methods. Active or interactive methods involve the stimulation of cognitive activity and learner autonomy. Interactive methods are aimed at creating a comfortable learning environment where all students actively communicate with each other. The organization of interactive education includes the modeling of life conditions, the use of role-playing games, the general solution of information based on the analysis of tasks and situations, the introduction of information flows into the mind, which causes its active activity. An integral part of interactive approaches are interactive exercises and tasks performed by students. The main difference between interactive exercises and regular work is that they are aimed not only at consolidating the learned material, but also at learning new things [6].

Modern pedagogy is rich in many interactive approaches, including:

- creative tasks - work in small groups - educational games (role playing, imitation, business games and educational games)
- use of public resources (inviting specialists, excursions) — social projects (social projects, contests, radio and newspapers, films, demonstrations, exhibitions, performances, songs and tales)

— learning and strengthening of new materials (interactive working with lecture, demonstration manuals, video and audio materials, "student as teacher", "everyone teaches everyone")

— discussion of complex and controversial questions and problems. [7]

With the interactive education method, students communicate directly in the learning environment, which in turn serves as a source of experience. In the understanding of pedagogical methods, it implies the preparation of students and teachers when mutual relations are formed. He does not work as a student-listener or observer, but actively participates in the lesson. With this form of organization of the educational process, not only school, high school, college, and even higher education students become full participants. The task of the teacher is mainly to encourage independent activity, to find ways to achieve their goals [2]. Thus, by using various pedagogical technologies in the lesson, the process of teaching English can be viewed from a completely new perspective, new mechanisms of personality formation can be mastered, and quality results can be achieved under favorable conditions.

CONCLUSION

The conclusion is that today's era of globalization requires humanity to keep up with the times. Therefore, it is desirable for specialists of various fields to be able to communicate in several foreign languages in addition to having a perfect knowledge of their native language. It is no secret that on May 6, 2021, a meeting of video selectors was held under the chairmanship of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev regarding measures to improve the system of teaching foreign languages. In it, the head of our state said, "It's time to establish a new system for teaching foreign languages in our country, which will be a solid foundation for the future. Since we have set ourselves the goal of building a competitive country, from now on, graduates of schools, lyceums, colleges and universities must have a perfect knowledge of at least 2 foreign languages. This strict requirement should become the main criterion for the activity of the head of every educational institution", he said, bringing reforms in the field to a new level.

Use of innovative technologies in foreign language teaching and discussion of theoretical, methodological and practical issues of foreign language teaching in modern education are considered as priority issues. Considering the widespread use of technology and various websites in the study of various modern sciences. [8]The use of the above in the process of teaching and learning English is the most effective method. The use of such tools among language teachers, firstly, increases the interest of the language learner in learning the language, increases the ability to learn the

language very quickly, and secondly, it records high indicators in the effective organization of language courses. Therefore, every language teacher should have the ability to work with modern technologies and various websites.

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